

**THE PROVERB IS A SPECIFIC LINGUISTICAL AND COGNITIVE SPACE FOR
THE REALIZATION OF THE SPIRITUAL EXPERIENCE AND MORAL
VALUES OF THE PEOPLE
(IN MATERIALS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)**

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Annotation: This article describes the culturally and linguistically similar aspects of English and Uzbek proverbs.

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INTRODUCTION

A proverb is a type of saying that contains a piece of advice or simply contains truth or any other universalvalue. It is a short statement that is popular and people make use of a proverb to express their feelings. A proverb can say a lot more than a thousand words. Morality, truth, wisdom, friendship, loyalty, etc. are the values that are glorified with the use of these proverbs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Proverb can be used in a literal or figurative sense in oral and written speech. Some proverbs are only used in a figurative ("Qarg'a qarg'aning ko'zini cho'qimaydi" ("Crows do not pick crow's eyes"), "Quruq qoshiq og'iz yirtar" ("An empty hand is no lure for a hawk")), or literal sense ("Ona yurtning omon bolsa, rangi-roying somon bolmas" ("If your country prospers, you prosper"))).

Proverbs are rich and diverse in terms of themes used. There are proverbs which are dedicated to such themes as motherland, labor, knowledge, skill, friendship, unity, wisdom, vigilance, language and speech culture, love, bad qualities, etc. Typical features of proverbs are: a dialectic unity of content and form; sometimes they are rich in rhymes; sometimes they have many meanings; they are metaphorical.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a proverb often it is possible to find such a phenomenon as antithesis (for example, "Kattaga hurmatda bol, kichikka izzatda" ("Honor the older, respect the younger")). Proverbs can also be prosaic and in verse forms. Although such proverbs as "Mehnat, mehnatning tagi rohat" ("Work is done, time for fun") are found in prose, it is still possible to feel poetic motifs in them. Also, much like in poems, there are inner motifs and rhymes in such proverbs as "Elga bersang oshingni, ellar silar boshingni. Itga bersang oshingni, itlar g`ajir boshingni" ("Give your food to the people and they will pat your head. Give your food to the dogs, and they will gnaw your head").

Examples of proverbs of Turkic people were provided for the first time in the work of Mahmud al-Kashgari called "Diwanu-Lugat al-Turk". Many of these proverbs, which have a variety of versions, are still used among Uzbek people. For example the proverb, which is provided by Mahmud al-Kashgari, "Kishi olasi ichtin, qilqi olasi tashtin" ("Human's mischief is hidden inside, in animals - outside"), is nowadays used in the form of "Odam olasi ichida, mol olasi tashida". In Uzbek language to denote proverbs (maqol) some other words are sometimes used. These are: "masal", "zarbulmasal", "naql", "hikmat", "hikmatli soz", "tanbeh", "mashoyikhlr so`zi", "hikmatli maqol", "donishmandlar sozi", "otalar sozi", etc. In general, proverbs are of great socio-political and educational value.

The following sayings are widespread among the people: "Qil uchida turibman" ("I hang in the balance"), "Semizlinki qo`y ko`taradi" ("Fatness is the right fit for a ram"), "Tuyaga yantoq kerak bolsa, boynini chozar" ("If camel needs a bur, it stretches its neck"), "Bekorga mushuk oftobga chiqmaydi" ("Without reason no cat comes out").

Proverb is a brief saying that presents a truth or some bit of useful wisdom. It is usually based on common sense or practical experience. The effect of a proverb is, to make the wisdom it tells seem to be self-evident. The same proverb often occurs among several different peoples. True proverbs are sayings that have been passed from generation to generation primarily by word of mouth. They may also have been put into written form.

A proverb consists of a short sentence which contains a general piece of wisdom. A proverb contains wisdom which has been handed down from one generation to the next. It describes situations which happened before and which are repeated again and again.

There are distinguished various types of the proverbs by their location:

Universal proverbs - On comparing proverbs of culturally unrelated parts of the world, one finds several ones having not only the same basic idea but the form of expression, i.e. the wording is also identical or very similar. These are mainly simple expressions of simple observations or simple ethical concepts, but not all expressions of simple observations became proverbs in every language.

Regional proverbs - In culturally related regions - on the pattern of loan-words - many loan-proverbs appear beside the indigenous ones. A considerable part of them can be traced back to the classical literature of the region's past, in Europe the Greco-Roman classics, and in the Far East to the Sanskrit and Korean classics.

Local Proverbs - In a cultural region often internal differences appear, the classics (e.g. the Bible or the Confucian Analects) are not equally regarded as a source of proverbs in every language. Geographical vicinity gives also rise to another set of common local proverbs. These considerations are illustrated in several European and Far-Eastern languages, as English and Korean.

Proverbs were always the most vivacious and at the same time the most stable part of the national languages, suitable competing with the sayings and aphorisms of

outstanding thinkers. In the proverb and sayings pictures queness of national thinking was more vivid expressed as well as their features of national character. The proverbs and sayings are the paper of folklore which is short but deep in the meaning. They

express the outlook of the amount of people by their social and ideal functions. Proverbs and sayings include themselves the some certain features of historical development and the culture of people.

There are six basic types of proverbs:

According to Meider W., proverbs by their meaning and motivation can be divided into six basic types:

Synonyms is a proverb in which both lines say essentially the same thing but expressed in a slightly different way.

E.G. Deeds are fruits, words are but leaves Antithetical means that a thought is presented in the first line, with the negative of that thought expressed in the second line.

E.G. Actions speak louder than words Synthetic is when both lines seem to express totally different thoughts, even opposite thoughts, yet which have one common theme.

Integral is when the second line completes the thought of the first line. E.G. Don't trouble troubles until troubles trouble you!

Parabolic is when the first line illustrates the second. The second line is the teaching the first one is the analogy. E.G. All is well that ends well. Comparative is when a proverb compares one thing with another to illustrate a common trait.

E.G. Blood is thicker than water.

CONCLUSION

So, proverb is a genre of oral folk art. It is a wise adage, which is short, figurative and grammatically and logically complete, a phrase with a deep meaning. Proverbs, which have certain, steady and widely used rhythmic formula, emerged on the basis of people's centuries-long experience. In proverbs found its reflection people's life-related observations, their attitudes to the society, their history, spiritual state, ethical and aesthetic feelings and positive qualities. Having been preserved by the people throughout centuries, they acquired concise and simple poetic form.

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